

Effect of 3 methods of raising rice seedlings on leaf water potential and fresh weight, 1989. ^a

Seedling age (d)	Leaf water potential (Pa)			Fresh weight (g/plant)				
	WN	DN	DWN		WN	DN	DWN	
			10 d	20 d			10 d	20 d
35	7.7	1.1	1.05		1.1	1.2	1.2	
45	1.0	1.1	1.06	1.04	1.4	1.2	1.7	1.7
55	1.0	1.1	0.95	0.95	1.2	1.3	1.4	1.7
65	0.96	1.2	0.97	1.04	3.2	2.3	2.6	2.6
LSD (0.05) = 0.6			LSD (0.05) = 0.3					

^a Mean of 5 cultivars or lines. WN = wet nursery; DN = dry nursery; DWN = dry-wet nursery.

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Effect of N application timing on ratoon rice

K. Srinivasan, National Pulses Research Centre, Pudukkottai 622303; and S. Purushothaman, Agricultural College, Madurai 625104, India

N rate and frequency are critical factors in managing rice ratoon crops. We studied split N application during 1988 wet season.

The ratoon crop received 100-50-50 kg NPK/ha. N was applied to medium-duration rice varieties Ponni and Bhavani as complete basal immediately after harvest of main crop; half as basal and half 30 d after harvest of main crop (DH); and one-third as basal, one-third 15 DH, and one-third 30 DH. The experiment was laid out in

Effect of N application timing on ratoon yield. Madurai, India, 1988 wet season.

Variety	Yield (t/ha) at given time of N application			
	Complete basal	Two splits	Three splits	Mean yield (t/ha)
Ponni	2.0	1.7	1.6	1.8
Bhavani	3.0	2.7	2.6	2.8
Mean	2.5	2.2	2.1	
	SE±	LSD (0.05)		
Variety	0.118	0.263		
Time of N	0.142	0.294		
Interaction	0.203	ns		

a factorial randomized block design with three replications. Soil was sandy clay loam with pH 7.3.

Bhavani produced significantly higher ratoon yield (2.8 t/ha, 50% of its main crop yield). All N as basal

produced a ratoon yield of 2.5 t/ha (see table). Basal application significantly improved all yield attributes and grain and straw yields, probably because of early sprouting and healthy ratoon tillers. □

Yield of rice sown in standing water

L. Saikia, A. K. Pathak, and B. P. Baruah, Regional Agricultural Research Station, Assam Agricultural University, Titabar 785630, Assam, India

In large areas of Assam, flooding frequently destroys the wet season rice crop transplanted in Jul. In such situations, farmers direct seed rice in Sep, when floodwaters have receded. We experimented with sowing in standing water, to move direct seeding to earlier in the season.

Cultivars Culture 1 and CR666-68 were tested on a clay loam soil

during 1988 wet season. Two seed treatments were used: soaking in water 12 h and soaking until seed sprouted. Seeds were sown in 12 cm standing water on 25 Aug; water depth was maintained for 12 d.

In both varieties, nonsprouted

seed germinated well and more seedlings emerged better than those from sprouted seed. Panicle weight and grain yield were significantly higher with nonsprouted seeds (see table). Panicles/m² did not differ significantly. Yield differences were possibly

Influence of underwater sowing on yield and yield-related attributes of rice. Titabar, India, 1988.

Variety	Method	Panicles (no./m ²)	Panicle weight (g)	Grain yield (t/ha)
Culture 1	Nonsprouted	192	1.94	2.2
Culture 1	Sprouted	164	1.88	1.6
CR666-68	Nonsprouted	190	1.89	2.0
CR666-68	Sprouted	166	1.86	1.5
LSD (0.05)		24	0.09	0.2